

A Future Vision to promote Intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

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Abstract

The study-in-progress attempts to ensuring the importance of the African market for the Egyptian tourism industry alongside the other tourist markets, and achieving the African integration through intra-regional tourism. The main objective of this study is to present future visions and strategies to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa. Intra-regional tourism is providing social interest and leisure opportunities, supporting community infrastructure and industry, and ultimately contributing to social cohesion and national pride. Data was collected through questionnaire list and interviews with experts at Ministry of Tourism and researchers at the Institute of African Research and Studies, Cairo University. The findings revealed that intra-regional tourism plays an important role to deal with many political, economic, social and cultural and environmental problems between Egypt and African countries. It indicated that the most important obstacles facing the promotion of intra-regional tourism are lack of promotional marketing campaigns, absence of policies and plans related to put African tourism on the Egyptian tourism map, the complex procedures for obtaining a visa to Egypt. The findings also suggested some of future visions to promote intra-regional tourism, the most prominent of which are Conducting a lot of market studies about African communities, implementing an organized marketing campaign to African Market, solving the problems and political tensions between Egypt and the African countries, launching regular flights with competitive prices, encouraging joint tourism programs between Egypt and the African countries for foreign tourists. Finally, the study concludes with suggestions for decision makers in Egypt to pay attention to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.

Keywords: Tourism, Intra-regional tourism, Egypt, Africa, African Tourism Movement.

1. Introduction

Tourism industry plays a vital role in the development of countries (Signè, 2018). It is one of the most important sources of national income for many countries around the world (OECD, 2016). It represents a major source of service exports, foreign exchange and employment (Christie et al., 2013; Naude and Saayman, 2005; Fayissa et al., 2008). Egypt's belonging to the African continent is deeply rooted in history, as Africa holds a special position in the Egyptian civilization (Abuzaid et al., 2019). Egypt is considered a regional power with substantial cultural and political influence, as well as being one of the largest and most varied economies in the region (Metwally and Punnett, 2017). Based on Egypt's civilizational weight and historical and regional role on both the Arab and African levels, Egypt is an important bridge for the Arab-African relations (Abdel-Sadek, 2016).

In the wake of the January 25 and June 30 Revolutions, Egypt sought to restore its role in Africa as being one of Egypt's national security spheres, especially in light of the historic ties and vital interests between Egypt and its African circle, as Egypt seeks to reinstate its historic role (Ministry Of Foreign Affairs, 2019) to affirm its Islamic identity, Arab origins, and African roots. Recent tourism trends in the African region indicate that there may be a number of untapped development opportunities in major emerging markets that require the attention of national tourism Administrations in the region. These include, in particular, the rapidly growing Chinese outbound market, sub-Saharan Africa and the intraregional Arab market (UNWTO Commission for the Middle East, 2014). Tourism is still limited contribution in most African countries' economy, which, if they make good

use of their natural resources and tourism assets, they will achieve the comprehensive and sustainable development of the peoples of these poor countries (The World Bank , 2011).

The problem of the study

Intra-regional tourism between countries in the same region had appreciable influence on the distribution of world arrivals. Of the total international tourist movements within North America and Europe, 75% are intra-regional. For South Asia, it may be estimated at 20-30% of the tourist flows are intra-regional. In Africa, intra-regional tourist movement may be estimated that nearly 40% (Bhatia, 2006:16). In this context, the problem of the study revolves around the importance of the African market for the Egyptian tourism industry alongside the other tourist markets, in view of the need to diversify the tourist markets to the Egyptian tourist destination and the importance of intra-regional tourism to achieve African integration, which is reflected on improving the political and economic consequences. The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- How can intra-regional tourism contribute to solve the political, social and cultural, economic and environmental problems in the Africa?;
- What are the most important obstacles facing the promotion of intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa?, and how can it be overcome?;
- What are the most important future visions and strategies to increase intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa?;
- What are the most important African markets that should be started to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa ?; and
- What are the most important types of tourism that should be focused on to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa?.

Importance of the Study

The importance of the study is highlighted in coinciding with Egypt's presidency of African Union in 2019, as well as increasing cooperation between Egypt and African countries in various industrial, trade, investment, and tourism, in addition to Egypt's hosting for many African sporting events and competitions (Africa Cup of Nations 2019) and The Arab and African Youth Platform in 2019, that provides a great opportunity to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African Countries.

The Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research is to present future visions and strategies to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.. So, the study attempts achieve these objectives:

- Recognize the concept of intra-regional tourism and to review the global movement of African tourism.
- Study the current intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.
- Study the most important obstacles and problems that may hinder the promotion of intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.
- Suggest the most important future visions and strategies to increase intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.

The review of the existing literature clarifies a gap in previous research, which indicates that the absence of studies - within the limits of the researcher's knowledge- dealt with intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African. The previous studies dealt with Intra-regional tourism in general as a part of reports and Publications for international and African organizations (The World Bank, 2011; UNCTAD 14, 2016; UNCTAD, 2017; NYU et al., 2011), and some case studies (Green and George, 2009; Mayaka and Prasad , 2012; Jeurung, 2016). The recent study was an initial attempt to fill this gap in previous studies related to intra-regional tourism. This study makes important contributions in fulfilling this gap through studying the intra-regional movements to African tourists to

Egypt, and presenting some future visions and strategies for promoting intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries.

2. Literature review

2.1. Intra-regional tourism Definition

Intra-regional tourism is relatively less significant in developing region (Africa, South Asia) as compared to developed regions (Europe, America). However, the significance of intra-regional tourism is likely to vary between different regions and from one country to another (Verma, 2019). Intra-regional tourism is known as regional tourism, represents a sub-category of international tourism, and refers to ‘intra-regional’ movement flows of tourists to and from countries within the same region (Rogerson, 2004). It has direct impact on the development of economic, political, social, and environment in the less developed regions (Verma, 2019).

Canavan (2013:349) stated that “Successful intra-regional tourism destinations are accessible to locals, providing social interest and leisure opportunities, supporting community infrastructure and industry, and ultimately contributing to social cohesion and civic pride”.

2.2. Africa and the World Tourism Movements

Africa is a small but expanding region of the global tourism economy (Rogerson, 2007). Africa continent consists of 54 countries, which divided between North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa (Saayman et al., 2018), each with their own unique culture, history, and natural wonders (AFDB, 2016). Tourism can be a powerful development path for Africa (Christie et al., 2014). Africa has a major opportunity to employ its tourism potential to enhance development and increase its participation in the global economy (UNWTO, 2015). Africa has a lot to offer that can no longer be found elsewhere in the world (Naude and Saayman, 2005). IT is truly embellished with a unique diversity, natural beauty resources, historical sites and cultural heritage, beaches, wildlife, deserts, safaris (UNWTO, 2015), traditions and customs and cultural events such as music, art dance and festivals, and much more that (Naude and Saayman, 2005; Christie et al., 2013). As indicated in Figure (1) the proportion of African tourists visiting the continent’s countries are concentrated in southern Africa, while the North African countries are more focused on attracting non-African tourists, which may indicate the interest of the Southern African countries to develop intra-regional tourism than the North African countries.

Figure 1: Percentage of tourist (Africa, Non-Africa) arrivals by continent of origin

Source: (Fourie and Santana-Gallego, 2011:16; Gisore and Ogutu, 2015:11)

“The total contribution of Travel & Tourism in Africa to GDP, as a direct and indirect contribution, was USD177.6bn (8.1% of GDP) in 2017, and is prediction to rise in 2018 by 3.7%, and to rise by 4.2% pa to USD278.2bn (8.1% of GDP) in 2028” (WTTC Africa, 2018:1). In 2016, Africa held a 3.0% share of worldwide tourism receipts, and a 5.1% share in worldwide tourism arrivals. In 2017, total tourism employment in Africa also experienced a steady rise, where travel and tourism jobs accounted for 6.5% of total employment or 22.8 million jobs (including direct, indirect, and induced employment); with 17.2 million jobs in sub-Saharan Africa, and 5.6 million jobs in North Africa (AFDB, 2018).

China contributed to the African tourism movement in 2012, where recorded top 5 African countries for Chinese arrivals as follows, Egypt (172,190), South Africa (145,930), Ethiopia (128,800), Algeria (83,040), and Kenya (44,270) (AFDB et al., 2013). Tourism has been negatively affected by terrorism in some countries (Burkina Faso, Egypt, Cameroon, Kenya and Tunisia). At the same time, tourism has grown in several countries in 2015 (Ethiopia, Madagascar, Mauritius, Rwanda, Seychelles, Zimbabwe) (AFDB et al., 2016)

In 2017 International tourist arrivals in Africa are estimated to have increase by 9% and receipts at the same level (+8%) (UNWTO, 2018) by 66,323 million tourists (ECA et al., 2018). Although this is seemingly modest, tourism in sub-Saharan Africa saw an 8.9% increase in international arrivals. Generally, the North African countries of Algeria, Morocco, Sudan, and Tunisia saw sustained growth at 5.0%, but the most drastic change in arrivals was seen by Egypt in 2016, which encountered a drop of 3.881 million tourist arrivals, a 42.5% decline from the previous year. However, Egypt’s arrivals for 2017 have rebounded and will be closer to prior figures. Accounting for tourism arrivals, Morocco, South Africa, Tunisia, Egypt, and Zimbabwe remain the top five African destinations. Notably in 2016, South Africa surpassed 10 million arrivals for the first time (with a 12.8% increase from 2015) and Morocco sustained more than 10 million arrivals for the fourth consecutive year. Aside from Egypt, each country in the top five saw an increase in

arrivals (AFDB, 2018). World Tourism Organization predicted an increase in the number of tourists traveling to Africa in 2030 to 134 million, representing 7.4 % of the global share (UNWTO, 2017) as shown in table (1).

Table 1: UNWTO tourism towards 2030: International tourism to African regions

Regions	International tourist arrivals received (million)					Share (%)	
	Actual data			Projections		2010	2030
	1980	1995	2010	2020	2030		
Africa	7.2	18.9	50.3	85	134	5.3	7.4
North Africa	4.0	7.3	18.7	31	46	2.0	2.5
West and Central Africa	1.0	2.3	6.8	13	22	0.7	1.2
East Africa	1.2	5.0	12.1	22	37	1.3	2.1
Southern Africa	1.0	4.3	12.6	20	29	1.3	1.6

Source: (UNWTO, 2017:15)

2.3. African Tourism Competitiveness

The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2017 Ranking issued by the world economic forum, which covering 136 countries, table (2) indicates the most important African countries according to The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2017 Ranking.

Table 2: The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index 2017 Africa

Region	Country	score	Rank/141 2015	Rank/136 2017
NORTH AFRICA	Morocco	3.8	62	65
	Egypt	3.6	83	74
	Tunisia	3.5	79	87
	Algeria	3.1	123	118
SOUTHERN AFRICA	South Africa	4.0	48	53
	Namibia	3.6	70	82
	Botswana	3.5	88	85
	Zambia	3.2	107	108
	Zimbabwe	3.1	115	114
EASTERN AFRICA	Mauritius	3.9	56	55
	Kenya	3.6	78	80
	Tanzania	3.4	93	91
	Uganda	3.2	114	106
	Ethiopia	3.1	118	116
WESTERN AFRICA	Cape Verde	3.6	86	83
	Côte d'Ivoire	3.2	119	109
	Senegal	3.1	112	111
	Gabon	3.1	124	119
	Ghana	3.0	120	120
	Cameroon	2.9	122	126
	Nigeria	2.8	131	129
	Mali	2.8	128	130

Source: (Preparation of the researcher based on the statistics contained in The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report 2017, 2017)

2.4. Intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Intraregional tourism is a harbinger to promote the region for international tourists particularly from the adjoining countries. It strengthens the capacity within the region to correct some of the common challenges faced by a region (Organization of Islamic Cooperation, 2017). Intraregional tourism remains the great segment of all international tourism in Africa (Ndiaye 2006). Timothy and Teye (2005:88–89) mentioned that the largest proportion of the intra-regional tourism is by road transportation due to the poor air, water and rail transportation systems in Africa. The World Tourism Organization in 2004 predicted that, in Africa, intra-regional tourism tourists will rise to 64% of all international tourism by 2020, with exceeding 50 million tourists, in comparison with 58% for 1995 (Ezeuduji, 2013).

Intra-regional tourism may be the great hope of African tourism. Already more than 10 million tourists are travelling across international borders every year within Africa for many purposes such as, shopping, sport trips, medical reasons, religious journeys, visiting friends and relatives, and conferences and business meetings, and.38 South Africa is the largest market for intra-regional leisure travel in Africa, accounting for about 47% of all intra-regional tourists. In East Africa, intraregional tourism is already significant. Nigeria is a potential intra-regional tourism weight in West Africa. Zimbabwe also has potential as a large source market for intra regional tourism. (The World Bank, 2011). UNWTO indicated that The majority of international tourism takes place within tourist's own regions, with about four out of five arrivals worldwide beginning in the same region (UNWTO, 2016.). It forecasts that 75% of all tourists to Africa will be intraregional African tourists by 2021. The pattern of travel in Africa is closely related to ethnic similarities, incomes commercial partners, and nearest neighbours (Gisore and Ogotu, 2015). As shown in Table (3), tourists from Europe and the Middle East represent the majority of international tourism to Egypt.

Table 3: International Tourism to Egypt by Regions 2013-2016

Arrivals by region	Unit	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total	(000)	9,464	9,878	9,328	5,399
Africa	(000)	399	399	418	498
Americans	(000)	240	244	294	279
East Asia and the Pacific	(000)	248	213	280	342
Europe	(000)	6,976	7,578	6,794	2,586
Middle East	(000)	1,494	1,343	1,422	1,581
South Asia	(000)	84	76	64	98
Other not classified	(000)	23	25	25	15

Source: (World Tourism Organization, 2019)

The Middle East and Africa have been among the world's fastest growing regions in the last years. In addition, investments and tourism flows between them have increased significantly in the past few years. Tourist movement from the Middle East to Africa, in particular North Africa including Egypt, have increased from 0.8 million to 3.1 million between 1995 and 2013, a 8% annual growth rate and 9% to a market share. Tourism flows from Africa to the Middle East have also increased by 8% annually between 1995 and 2013, growing from 0.6 million to 2.3 million and corresponding to a market share of 9% (UNWTO Commission for the Middle East, 2014). According to the African tourism' statistics coming to Egypt during the first half of 2016, 10.3% of total arrivals to Egypt coming from Africa (Rashed, 2016), While many Egyptian tourism experts pointed out that African tourism in Egypt does not exceed 1% (Ghonaim, 2015), which do not fit with the fact that Egypt has the highest tourism potential in the Arab and African region (Mansfeld and Winckler, 2004). As indicated in figure (4) the movements of African tourism arrivals to Egypt from 2012 to 2016.

Table 4: African Tourism arrivals to Egypt 2012-2016

African Regions	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Market Share 2016	% Change 2015-2016
Total	11,531,858	9,464,349	9,877,762	9,327,804	5,398,934	100.00	-42.12
Africa	428,168	398,910	396,703	418,404	498,302	9.23	19.10
East Africa	38,872	40,384	35,238	35,036	37,948	0.70	8.31
Central Africa	5,179	4,894	6,157	9,029	11,788	0.22	30.56
North Africa	296,964	260,668	275,525	303,982	374,148	6.93	23.08
Southern Africa	22,829	21,561	16,553	15,344	12,613	0.23	-17.80
West Africa	64,322	71,402	65,229	54,997	61,788	1.14	12.35

Source: (World Tourism Organization, 2017)

2.5. Barriers to promote Intraregional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

The major challenges and obstacles to the development of intra-regional tourism in African represented in Political instability (Haddad et al., 2015; UNECA,2011), weak governments, poor funding, low income and poverty problems (Naude and Saayma, 2005), lack of trained labor (Christie et al., 2014), difficulty of obtaining a travel visa (UNCTAD 14, 2016), Lack of infrastructure (Gisore and Ogutu, 2015; Fourie and Santana-Gallego,2011), high crime rates, unsafe roads, inadequate water, poor sanitation, high cost of electricity, poor construction practices, and lack of health facilities(The World Bank , 2011). In addition to the previous obstacles, there are other obstacles that will be reviewed in the following points:

2.5.1. The mental image of Arabs and Africans:

There is a negative mental image about the Arab and African citizens on the part of each others, which are linked to the views of superiority, and what is associated with the Arab slave trader, and between the two images, generated negative desires from each side to the other, (Abdel-Sadek), Hence, comes the important role of tourism in changing the mental image of a country in the minds of others, creating a positive national image, attracting more investment, enhancing national pride and serving as an engine of growth (The World Bank , 2011; Christie et al., 2014; Gisore and Ogutu, 2015).

2.5.2. Transport and shipping obstacles:

There are more than one billion people on the African continent, which is home to just 3% of the world's aviation business. It is clear that the continent remains in urgent need of improved and affordable aviation connectivity (Mariano, 2018). The airlines obstacles to travel between Africa are tremendous. The air ticket prices are some of the most expensive in the world, the difficult for African airlines to get flying rights between major African cities (El-Houry, 2017). A decrease in transportation costs is likely to increase the demand for international tourism, and vice-versa (Green and George, 2009). As well as the poor quality of airport infrastructure in the majority of the African continent and the number of seats available for domestic and international flights (UNECA, 2015; Crotti and Misrahi, 2015). Regional cooperation as a means of building a beneficial infrastructure helps to strengthen the ability of countries to trade and to promote intra-regional tourism between African countries, as well as the free movement of African citizens (AFDB et al, 2014). Moreover, regional integration can promote tourism in Africa by facilitating and investing in transport, particularly air transport (Organization of Islamic Cooperation, 2017). In addition, the failure to establish railways and land routes between African countries are hindering the development of intra-regional tourism.

2.5.3. Administrative and procedural obstacles (Visa requirements):

Complex and routine procedures represent the main obstacles to the promotion of intra-regional-tourism (Crotti and Misrahi, 2015). The most important of which is obtaining visas (UNCTAD 14, 2016). There are many opportunities to expand intra-regional African tourism by reducing barriers to the movement of Africans (AFDB et al., 2013). A 2014 study undertaken jointly by the World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) and the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) argued that Supporting visa facilitation, including regional visa cooperation and e-visa, has led to enormous economic benefits for countries that adopted this approach (AFDB et al., 2015). Improving visa procedures could create an additional US\$206 billion for the tourism sector alone, and generate 5.1 million new jobs by 2015 in the G20 countries (AFDB et al., 2013). If the visa is too difficult to obtain or too expensive, tour operators may decide to not include the country in a regional tour, where visa facilities, as in Mozambique and Madagascar, tourism growth increased (Christie et al., 2013). A study on Tour operators in the United States and United Kingdom indicated that there are a higher proportion of tourists to Sub-Saharan Africa travel to other parts of the world because of the complex procedures of obtaining visas, booking accommodation, and arrangements of the tour (Gisore and Ogutu, 2015).

Africans are required Visas to travel to 55% of the countries in the continent. If somebody wants to travel from one country to another country, he may need to go to third country to obtain a Visa to travel, which represents a big burden on tourists (El-Houry, 2017). Furthermore, the improved visa requirements make most of African countries accessible for tourists. Some African countries offer a visa on arrival, while others requiring a lengthy wait for visa procedures through an embassy or consulate (Mariano, 2018). In some cases, the required documents have to be translated into the official language of the country issuing the visa, if the documents are in other languages (AFDB, 2016). The African Union's Agenda 2063 included a suggestion to remove visa requirements for travel by Africans within the continent, there is a response with countries removing visa requirements or issuing "visa on arrival" policies for Africans (Signè, 2018).

2.5.4. Political and Economic Obstacles:

Any instability caused by political or economic crises directly affect Egypt's tourism (Metwally and Punnett, 2017). The economic impact of political instability may be long lasting, displaying a negative image of a tourist destination, even if it may have been of short duration. Political and economic instability can have an impact on the marketing decisions of tour operators and the investment (UNCTAD, 2017). To relieve these risks, it is critical to implement technological and innovative operations that can increase both the security and efficiency of travel. There is a need to consider how to implement improvements in early warning systems, crisis management, visa procedures, data sharing. The main challenge is to create indispensable levels of cooperation among governments, the private sector, and international institutions (Gisore and Ogutu, 2015). There are also, many economic obstacles in Africa, such as the African communities' conflict, weak institutional capacity, and poor governance (Christie et al., 2014). In addition to high cost of travel and transport (The World Bank, 2011), and the currencies' exchange rate between the countries (Naude and Saayman, 2005).

2.5.5. Security, Safety and Health Obstacles:

Security concerns can result in instant stopping of tourism in a country (Christie et al., 2013; AFDB et al., 2016). The feeling of safety is one of the most important factors affecting the choice of tourist destination (ITB Report, 2016; UNECA, 2011). Ultimately, the travel and tourism industry's survival is depended on Providing a safe travel experience for tourists away from threats, acts of violence and terrorism (Crotti and Misrahi, 2015; Gisore and Ogutu, 2015; Government of South Africa, 1996). In this respect, health safety should also be mentioned. The outbreak of diseases and epidemics in some African countries such as the Ebola and Malaria instilled fear into travellers travelling to the continent (Mariano, 2018). In addition, access to clean drinking water, sanitation facilities, and the quality of food and beverages provided, which are challenging for many African

countries (Signè, 2018; Gisore and Ogutu, 2015; Crotti and Misrahi, 2015; UNECA, 2011).

Water security is an important issue and threat facing Egypt especially with the Nile-basin countries. Here comes the role of intra-regional tourism in achieving rapprochement between Egypt and Africa, especially with the Nile-basin countries through developing a new approach based on the concept of sharing and cooperation not to conflict (Noffel, 2013).

2.6. Visions and Strategies to promote Intraregional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Africa has long had success in tourism. Currently, it is repositioning itself in the tourism market by offering several experiences to travelers and making tourism more accessible (Mariano, 2018). There are some of visions and strategies that will be reviewed in the following points:

2.6.1. Activation policies and plans to place Africa on the Egyptian tourism map

The tourist product flourishes in any country when the tourism sector is well managed through the cooperation and coordination between the government - represented by the Ministry of Tourism, the private sector and civil society organizations in general, and especially among the communities affected by tourism (Christie et al., 2013; The World Bank, 2011). Rashed (2016) argued that best practices in destination management and exchanging knowledge as well as promoting investments are key development drivers in the African countries. The first language in most African countries may not be English, French, Portuguese, or Spanish; it is usually a tribal language (Christie et al., 2014). Therefore, there should be plans and policies that take into account the cultural and linguistic identity of the African continent, with more attention being paid to the teaching of the main and more widespread African languages such as Hausa and Swahili.

In this context, as part of wide media discourse to Africa, Egypt's State Information Service (SIS) launched a website portal in six languages, Arabic, English, French, Swahili and Hausa with the Amharic, as an attempt to communicate with the African people in their local languages beside the European languages spread in the African continent, and the Arabic language. These steps encourage Egyptians to be more aware of African countries, Egypt's relations with them, their cultures, news, literature, economies, symbols, histories and civilizations (Egypt Independent, 2019).

2.6.2. Activating the role of soft power in Egypt's relations with African countries

Soft power is the ability to shape the preferences of others through a country's appeal and attraction and harness international alliances. It also refers to the ability to influence the thinking of people, and change their behavior through the spread of dialogue, cultural exchanges, and ideas (Sayed, 2017). In the Arab world, Egypt has been long recognized for its own brand of soft power. For the past century, Egypt has also been the most important center for artists, scholars, intellectuals, and authors who have played an essential role in shaping Egyptian society and influencing Arab and African populations around the world (Sayed, 2017). Soft power is the most important tool of the Egyptian state in carrying out its domestic and foreign policies to beat the discourse of violence, hatred, and extremism, and promoting peaceful coexistence between societies. The Egyptian state's need for soft power now is large and still growing, given the regional and global challenges it faces (El-Menawy, 2018).

Abdel-Dayem -Minister of Culture- announces Egypt's cultural map that will be organized in Africa, ensuring that the soft power as a bridge of communication between nations. The program supports and enhances the cultural and artistic activities between Egypt and Africa, including 110 activities in all fields, the participation of African countries in the 51 Edition of Aswan International Festival for Culture and Arts", " Cairo International Film Festival", The 7th International Forum of Folkloric Heritage - entitled The interaction between Arab and African Heritage", Luxor International Photography Forum " with interactive events in different African countries". In addition to organizing a number of cultural and cinematic weeks in Egypt and African countries, organizing "African Youth

Innovations Competition", and organizing the conference of "African Is Egypt Heart ", as well as many other cultural events (Ministry of Culture, 2019). Moreover, the foreign ministry launched a campaign for soft power aims at highlighting Egyptian art and culture in order to spread Egypt's civilization and humanitarian messages through launching cultural activities worldwide (State information Service, 2018).

2.6.3. Marketing and promotion the Egyptian tourist destinations in Africa:

Tourism marketing and promotional activities as a policy tool aims to influence the performance of tourism destinations. Importantly, Tourism marketing strategies can have significant inclusions in terms of the social structure of tourist regions and the opportunities and restrictions for stakeholders to engage in tourism (Jeuring, 2016). Building a positive image about the country is especially important where political instability, famine, civil war, or health disease have occurred (Signè, 2018). Egypt's tourism and marketing policy in Africa should be undergoing radical changes, including creating an international integration between different agencies and companies, and also focusing on the distinctive characteristics of the Egyptian character and the different distinctive features of the tourist destinations in Egypt (El-Bakry, 2019). Rashid (2016) indicated that the Egyptian local products should be an essential component of the destination brand and should be integrated in the marketing campaigns. As well as the using of joint marketing programs can be used as a tool for promoting intra-regional tourism in the African Region (UNCTAD 14, 2016). Over the long term, the successful of Africa's tourism market will depend on preserving effective partnerships with the public sector and improving relationships with the local community (Signè, 2018).

Technological developments continue to play a key vital role in the tourism industry (Mayaka and Prasad, 2012). Due to the importance of e-marketing and social networking sites and their impact on the global tourism movement, the Egyptian ministry of tourism has used a number of social media platforms and influential media outlets to broadcast positive messages about Egypt (Ali, 2019). In this context, the number of US tourists traveling to African countries increased by 15% through the Internet. Egypt, Tanzania, Zimbabwe and South Africa also attract a lot of attention from users' Internet around the world through search engines (NYU Africa House et al., 2011). In this context, The State Information Service (SIS) should play an important role to correct the mental image of Egypt in African countries and vice versa, through achieving cultural communication, developing the media discourse and information awareness, and building bridges of understanding and trust between Egypt and African countries (Abuzaid et al., 2019).

3. Methodology

The methodology included a survey list and personal interviews with tourism representatives and experts, in order to answer the study questions and achieve the objectives of the study.

3.1. Sampling and Data collection:

The target respondents of the study include the category "A" tourism companies in Cairo. A random sample was chosen from the employees of these companies due to the nature of their direct work with the external and internal tourism markets, whether existing or targeted. This makes them aware of the needs and desires of these markets, including the African market. Data were collected by distributing a questionnaire form on employees and by using an online survey. (196) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the selected sample. Only 173 respondents agreed to complete the survey with a response rate of (88.3%). However, 23 copies (11.7%) were excluded.

3.2. Measures

In order to answer the study questions, a well-structured questionnaire was designed and distributed. It included in its first part demographic data, followed by two questions about the percentage of African tourist coming to Egypt, and the extent of worth promotion intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa. It included five sections in second part

about the contribution of intra-regional tourism to solve problems in Africa, the most important obstacles, the most important future visions and strategies, the most important African markets that should be started to, and the most important tourist patterns that should be focused on in order to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa. Respondents were asked to rate their opinion using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1=Strongly disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree and 5=Strongly agree. The statistical analysis of the data was done using SPSS V.25.

4. Data Analysis and Results

Table (5) presents the demographic characteristics of respondents. The sample was included (63%) male and (37%) female. In terms of employment duration, the majority of respondents of 2-10 years (57.8%) and most of them were employees and Heads of the Departments (75.4%). In terms of education, the majority of respondents have a high education (78.6%).

Table (5) Demographic Characteristics

Gender	Frequency	% (n=173)
Male	109	63
Female	64	37
Duration of employment	Frequency	% (n=173)
Less than 2 Years	29	16.8
2-10 Years	100	57.8
More than 10 Years	44	25.4
Education	Frequency	% (n=173)
Secondary	9	5.2
High	136	78.6
Others	28	16.2
Occupation	Frequency	% (n=173)
Manager	42	24.3
Head of the Department	62	35.8
Employee	69	39.9

According to figure (2), 76.9% of respondents indicated that The percentage of African tourism coming to Egypt is 1-5%, while 20.2% indicated that the percentage is 6-10. It is a very small percentage that does not fit with the various tourist attractions in Egypt.

Figure 2: The percentage of African tourism coming to Egypt

As shown in figure (3), (79.1%) of respondents believe that there is merit for promoting intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa and should be more interested than it is now.

Figure 3: The Worth of promoting Intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Table (6) demonstrates the descriptive statistics for the contribution of intra-regional tourism in solving the economic, social and cultural, environmental, and political problems between Egypt and African countries. As shown in table (6), intra-regional tourism contributes to solve the political problems between Egypt and Africa was the highest mean (4.06) with a standard deviation of (.395), followed by the contribution of intra-regional tourism to solve economic, environmental, social and cultural problems with means (4.00, 3.94, 3.68) and with standard deviations (.492, .780, .468) respectively.

Table (6) Descriptive statistics for the contribution of intra-regional tourism in solving the economic, social and cultural, environmental, and political problems between Egypt and African countries

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
Solving economic problems:		
Intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa contributes to:	4.00	.492
✓ Increase tourism investments.	3.49	1.232
✓ Provide more of job opportunities.	4.01	.852
✓ Improve relations and increasing the prospects for cooperation and common interests.	4.50	.501
Solving Social and Cultural Problems:		
Intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa contributes to:	3.68	.468
✓ Increase the knowledge and culture exchange, customs and traditions between Egypt and Africa.	3.49	1.054
✓ Change the mental image about the African tourist.	3.62	1.059
✓ Increase the number of African research and studies to identify the customs, traditions and lifestyles of the African societies.	3.94	.729
✓ increase the number of scholarships between the students of Egypt and African countries	3.66	.905
Solving Environmental Problems:		
Intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa contributes to:	3.94	.780
✓ Preserve tourism resources (natural, environmental, archaeological	4.09	.722
✓ Raise tourism and environmental awareness between the citizens.	4.05	.667
✓ Change the behavior patterns of tourists towards the environmental and natural resources.	3.68	.951
Solving Political Problems:		
Intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa contributes to:	4.06	.395
✓ Achieve political and social stability between Egypt and the African continent..	4.18	.753
✓ Spread the principles of peace and political stability between Egypt and African countries.	3.90	.771
✓ The positive results of intra-regional tourism at the economic, social and environmental levels will overcome many political problems between Egypt and the African countries.	4.11	.686

Table (7) indicates the Obstacles to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa. As shown in table (7), The six most important obstacles were Lack of the Egyptian tourism offices in the African countries with mean (4.72), Absence of policies and plans related to put African tourism on the Egyptian tourism map (4.61), Lack of marketing and promotional efforts directed to the African market (4.43), Lack of marketing research related to the study of needs and desires of African societies (4.38), Focusing the policies and plans to attract European tourism and neglect its African counterpart (4.29), then Lack of statistics and data required on the African market related to tourism plans and studies preparation (4.27). In addition a set of other obstacles shown in the table.

Table (7) Descriptive statistics for the Obstacles to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Lack of field studies to develop tourism cooperation between Egypt and African countries.	4.24	.557
2. Lack of infrastructure and facilities in most African countries.	4.31	.501
3. Lack of statistics and data required on the African market related to tourism plans and studies preparation.	4.27	.540
4. Lack of the Egyptian tourism offices in the African countries.	4.72	.865
5. The high cost of flights for some citizens of African countries.	3.81	.676
6. Lack of marketing research related to the study of needs and desires of African societies.	4.38	.487
7. Absence of policies and plans related to put African tourism on the Egyptian tourism map.	4.61	.489
8. Absence of regular flights between Egypt and some African countries.	4.01	.690
9. Focusing the policies and plans to attract European tourism and neglect its African counterpart.	4.29	.457
10. Lack of contact with tour operators in the African continent.	3.97	.516
11. Security instability and the spread of infectious diseases in most African countries.	4.01	.581
12. Lack of marketing and promotional efforts directed to the African market.	4.43	.496
13. Political instability in most African countries.	3.32	1.067
14. Difficulty obtaining, delaying and high costs of visas.	3.92	.571

Table (8) indicates the future visions and strategies to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa. As shown in table (8), the agreement of all respondents about the future proposed visions and strategies. The six most important visions and strategies were solving the problems and political tensions between Egypt and the African Countries with mean (4.56), Pay attention to marketing research and studies related to the needs and desires of African societies (4.38), Using social networking sites for developing intra-regional tourism between the citizens of African countries (4.35), Involving the local communities of African countries in the tourism development (4.29), Increasing tourism and social awareness of the role of tourism in the economic development of the African countries (4.21), then Enhancing security stability in the tourism areas of the African countries (4.16). In addition a set of other visions and strategies shown in the table.

Table (8) Descriptive statistics for the future visions and strategies to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Enhancing security stability in the tourism areas of the African countries.	4.16	.558
2. Increasing tourism and social awareness of the role of tourism in the economic development of the African countries.	4.21	.603
3. Involving the local communities of African countries in the tourism development.	4.29	.457
4. Pay attention to marketing research and studies related to the needs and desires of African societies.	4.38	.487
5. Using social networking sites for developing intra-regional tourism between the citizens of African countries.	4.35	.697
6. Making research and academic studies on ways to increase Egyptian-African	4.05	.583

cooperation in the field of tourism.		
7. Development of the Egyptian tourist product and the creation of new tourist patterns that correspond to the desires and needs of African societies.	4.16	.409
8. Solving the problems and political tensions between Egypt and the African Countries.	4.56	.509
9. Establishing exhibitions of local products of African societies in Egypt in order to motivate the citizens of those countries to travel and marketing their products in Egypt.	4.02	.469
10. Increasing the number of scholarships for the African citizens in the Egyptian universities.	3.98	.638
11. Issuing a united visa between the African countries.	3.94	.617
12. Operating regular flights between Egypt and African countries and reducing airfares.	3.94	.588
13. Inviting experts and writers of tourism in familiarization trips to identify the Egyptian tourism product.	3.97	.614
14. Inviting African film producers to Egypt to show the Egyptian tourism destinations in their films.	3.90	.674
15. Increasing the number of Egyptian tourism offices in the African countries.	3.98	.669
16. Establishing an African city in Egypt containing the manifestations of life in Africa countries (e.g. customs and traditions, clothing, accommodation, meals, etc.).	3.72	.678
17. Implementing an advertising campaign to promote the Egyptian tourism product in Africa.	4.13	.334

Table (9) shows the most important African markets that should be started in order to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa. The markets were divided according to the African regions (examples of countries in each region were provided to assist the respondents). The Nile Basin countries came as the first countries to be started, stressing the role of tourism in removing tensions and differences of political views - and vice versa - which is reflected positively on the promotion intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries. The East African countries came in the second ranking, followed by West African countries in the third ranking. South African countries, North African countries, and central African countries came in the fourth, fifth, and sixth ranking respectively.

Table (9) the most important African markets to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa

Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Ranking
The Nile Basin Countries*	-	-	4	124	45	1
North African countries: (Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria, Sudan)	-	55	40	71	7	5
West African Countries: (Nigeria, Ghana, Niger, Benin, Côte d'Ivoire, Burkina Faso, Senegal, Mali, Mauritania, etc.)	-	-	43	121	9	3
South African Countries: (South Africa, Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, Swaziland)	-	14	63	71	25	4
East African Countries: (Kenya, Seychelles, Mauritius, Zambia, Ethiopia, Uganda, Somalia, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, etc.)	-	1	18	136	18	2
Central African Countries: (Cameroon, Angola, Gabon, Chad, the Congo, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, etc.)	11	39	71	42	10	6

¹ - The Nile Basin countries have been placed with the African regions in a separate item, due to the political tension between Egypt and some Nile Basin countries. These tensions have a negative impact on increasing the intra-regional tourism.

Table (10) shows the most important tourist types to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa. Medical tourism came as the first types to be focused on, which may be due to the spread of many diseases and epidemics in the African continent, which represents an opportunity for Egypt to attract the citizens of African countries for treatment. Recreational tourism and sport tourism came in the second and third ranking respectively, which represents an opportunity for Egypt to attract the African countries' tourists who have a passion for recreational and sports competitions, especially competitions related to football. Conference and festivals tourism came in the fourth rank. Egypt can increase intra-regional tourism with Africa through participating in African conferences and festivals, whether by organizing or hosting or actively participating in it. Safari tourism, educational tourism, cultural and heritage tourism, religious tourism, wildlife watch tourism, shopping tourism, business tourism, and ecotourism came from the fifth to the twelfth ranking.

Table (10) the most important tourist types to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa

Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Ranking
Religious tourism	4	12	37	107	13	8
Cultural and Heritage tourism	9	10	28	100	26	7
Recreational tourism	-	3	17	121	32	2
Educational tourism	6	15	25	110	17	6
Ecotourism / natural tourism	4	41	47	44	37	12
wildlife Watch Tourism	23	13	24	89	24	9
Medical tourism	-	3	10	124	36	1
Sport tourism	-	4	20	118	31	3
conferences and festivals Tourism	-	11	35	102	25	4
Safari Tourism	1	21	24	107	20	5
Shopping tourism	-	22	51	80	20	10
Business tourism	5	36	36	80	16	11

5. Interviews

Qualitative research has been adopted as a part of inquiry in the recent study. Qualitative approach was the most appropriate way to gather information required and to answer the research questions. Qualitative research focuses mainly on experiences and emotions and is designed to be probing in nature, thus encouraging informants to introduce concepts of importance from their perspective, rather than adhering to areas that have been pre-determined by the researcher (Altinay and Paraskevas, 2008:75; Abdulsamie, 2016). Semi-structured interviews have been chosen as data collection instrument. It is used to find out what is happening, seek new insights, identify general patterns and understand the relationship between variables (Brinkmann, 2014; Altinay and Paraskevas, 2008). A number of interviews were held with some experts and tourism representatives at Ministry of Tourism and the Egyptian tourism Authority, some Egyptian and African researchers at the Institute of African Research and Studies - Cairo University. The interview guide comprised nine open-ended questions. The interview questions included two questions; The first is related to the most important obstacles that facing the promotion of intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa, and the second is related to the most important visions and strategies to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa.

5.1. First: Obstacles of promoting intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa

The main obstacles are summarized in the following points:

- There are not enough promotional marketing campaigns for the Egyptian tourism product destined to Africa. Most of African citizens do not know much about the Egyptian tourism product and the tourist patterns in Egypt, and their suitability to them or not.

- The language factor is a major obstacle to the promotion of intra-regional tourism. In addition to the African languages, most African countries speak French, so they prefer to travel to Morocco, Tunisia and Algeria; where they speak the same language.
- The mental image about African tourists to many travel agencies' managers and employees in Egypt; concerning the fact that the African tourist is financially poor and will not represent a large addition to tourism revenues. It is a wrong mental image that needs to be changed.
- The procedures for obtaining a visa to Egypt, the delay in issuing it, and its high costs for the citizens of African countries, which makes them travel to other African countries that have canceled visas between them.
- The absence of direct regular flights between Egypt and most African countries, Which represents a burden on African tourists during travel from most African countries to Egypt.
- The lack of marketing and promotional campaigns directed to the African market, while focusing on the European market, especially the Russian market. These strategies make the Egyptian tourism lose millions of African tourists as an inbound tourism.
- There are no Egyptian tourist authority offices in Africa. Egypt's only office was located in South Africa. It was closed in 2000/2001. Only data from the Egyptian embassies in African countries is relied upon; while the Egyptian tourist offices abroad in many European countries are not effective.
- Some security considerations, which related to continuation of African tourists in Egypt and not returning to their countries.

5.2. Second: Future Visions and Strategies for to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa

All interviewees assured that the importance of the African market as a promising tourism market and the necessity of placing it on the Egyptian tourism map. The main strategies to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa are summarized in the following points:

- Conducting a lot of market studies about African communities and countries to identify their needs and desires and to estimate patterns of tourism that suit them.
- Making an organized marketing campaign to promote the Egyptian tourist product within the African continent, specifying the objectives and timing of each campaign and the target market.
- Direct contact with official bodies with the assistance of the Egyptian diplomatic representation, in order to strengthen the relations of cooperation between Egypt and African countries in the field of tourism and tourism investment. In addition, the necessity of opening tourist offices in more than one African country.
- Increasing the scholarships for the citizens of African countries in the Egyptian Universities. Many African countries are teaching the Egyptian history and civilization, such as Zimbabwe, which allows cooperating between Egypt and Zimbabwe in the field of tourism training and participation in tourist events between the two countries.
- The importance of teaching the African languages in Egyptian colleges and institutes, which represents a competitive advantage to deal with the African tourists and communicating with them in their own language.
- Actively Participation in African tourism exhibitions, such as WTMA, which is held in Cape Town, South Africa each year; as well as INDABA, which is held in Durban, South Africa. It is one of the largest tourism marketing exhibitions in Africa, and one of the three most important travel and tourism exhibitions in the world.
- Cooperation with specialized companies in e-marketing to market the Egyptian tourism in African countries.

- Making regular flights between Egypt and African countries with competitive prices.
- Encouraging joint tourism programs between Egypt and the African countries for foreign tourists and African tourists, so that the tourism program includes more than a tourism destination including Egypt and African countries. This is especially evident in Europe, especially that tourism from distant regions such as Latin America and Southeast Asia prefer to visit many countries in the same trip because of the high price of the flight ticket. African countries are characterized by cultural tourism such as Egypt, Tunisia, Libya and Morocco. Tanzania, Kenya and South Africa are characterized by wildlife watch tourism, Which provides good opportunities for organizing joint tourism programs.
- Taking care of medical tourism in Egypt and promoting it in the African continent by signing a protocol of cooperation between the Egyptian Tourism Authority, a specialized pharmaceutical company, and Egypt Air company. The Nigerian market, for example, is dominated by medical tourism. 600,000 Nigerian tourists in 2013, spending about \$ 400 million on medical tourism, and the most countries they have sought for treatment (India, Israel, Germany, Egypt "had a poor share"), and some 300,000 Nigerian tourists traveled to Dubai for shopping and entertainment.
- The importance of encouraging religious tourism between Egypt and the African countries, through the Holy Family path in Egypt, whereas the majority African citizens are Christians.
- Finding solutions to visa procedures of the African citizens through the coordination with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- Hosting African journalists through the Egyptian Tourism Authority in cooperation with African Journalists Union in order to implement familiarization trips for them in Egypt.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

Intra-regional tourism promotes regional integration through increased economic and trade activities, supports countries to better understand each other and collocates the way to identify common obstacles such as visa restrictions and some complex practices at customs (Organization of Islamic Cooperation, 2017). Despite the importance of the African market in the tourism industry, the proportion of African tourism coming to Egypt does not exceed 5%. Respondents noted that there is a great merit to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and African countries. It is supposed to receive more attention than it is now. Intra-regional tourism plays an important role to deal with many economic, social and cultural and environmental problems between Egypt and Africa. It contributes to deal with the political problems between Egypt and African countries, through working to achieve the political and social stability of the African countries, spreading the principles of peace, and overcoming many political tensions between Egypt and the African countries. The promotion of intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa is facing a series of obstacles, the most prominent of which are lack of promotional marketing campaigns destined to Africa, absence of policies and plans related to put African tourism on the Egyptian tourism map, the language obstacles, the negative mental image about African tourists, the complex procedures for obtaining a visa to Egypt, absence of direct regular flights between Egypt and most African countries, focusing marketing campaigns on the European market and ignoring the African market, there are no Egyptian tourist authority offices in Africa, Lack of marketing research related to the study of needs and desires of African societies, Lack of statistics and data required on the African market, and some security considerations related to continuation of African tourists in Egypt and not returning to their countries.

Respondents suggest some of future visions and strategies to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa, the most prominent of which are Conducting a lot of market studies about African communities and countries, implementing an organized

marketing campaign to promote the Egyptian tourist product within the African continent, solving the problems and political tensions between Egypt and the African, increasing the number of scholarships for the citizens of African countries in the Egyptian Universities, The importance of teaching the African languages in Egyptian colleges and institutes, actively Participation in African tourism exhibitions, such as WTMA and INDABA, Making regular flights between Egypt and African countries with competitive prices, encouraging joint tourism programs between Egypt and the African countries for foreign tourists and African tourists, Using social networking sites for developing intra-regional tourism, involving the local communities of African countries in the tourism development, encouraging religious tourism between Egypt and the African countries through the Holy Family path in Egypt, taking care of medical tourism in Egypt and promoting it in the African continent, finding solutions to visa procedures of the African citizens through the coordination with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and enhancing security stability in the tourism areas of the African countries. The Africa Visa Openness Report 2016 notes that, on average, an African national requires visas at departure for 55% of other African countries, does not need a visa for only 20% of those countries, and can obtain visas on arrival in only 25% of those countries. North Americans, for example, can travel more easily to African countries than most Africans (UNCTAD, 2017).

The most important African markets that should be started in order to promote intra-regional Tourism between Egypt and Africa are The Nile Basin countries, The East African countries, West African countries, South African countries, North African countries, and central African countries respectively. The most six important tourist types to promote intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa are medical tourism, recreational tourism, sport tourism, conference and festivals tourism, Safari tourism, educational tourism.

Based on the suggestions that were presented in the practical study, the recent study recommends the following:

- Strengthen the Egypt's foreign policy on African issues, and clarify the politically, economically and strategically importance of the African continent to Egypt.
- The need for effective policies and plans to put Africa on the Egyptian tourism map.
- Putting the importance of the African continent in the educational curricula, and emphasizing the identity of African Egypt, with similar attention to its Islamic and Arab identity.
- Supporting the Egyptian-African cultural cooperation through increasing the number of scholarships for Africans, teaching African languages in the Egyptian colleges and institutes, and establishing the Egyptian cultural offices in Africa.
- Increasing the number of information offices in the African continent, providing them with information materials on the Egyptian tourism, and developing the Egyptian media discourse towards correcting the negative concepts and mental image that formed among the Africans about Egypt.
- Organizing familiarization trips for tourists' writers, tour operators in the African continent to identify the Egyptian tourism patterns and tourist destinations.
- The importance of identifying the needs, desires, interests and types of tourism of the African markets in order to make tourist programs that suit them.
- Investment the Egypt's membership in the African economic blocs, such as COMESA, to enhance intra-regional tourism and trade between Egypt and the member countries in these blocs.
- Focusing on organizing and hosting the African exhibitions, conferences, and summits, which search for developing relations on all the economic, political, industrial, security, service and tourism levels, and to be held periodically in the Egyptian destinations.
- The need to take advantage of modern technologies and its tools, especially in the field of e-marketing and social networking sites to market intra-regional tourism between Egypt and Africa.

- Adoption and activation of the day of African tourism, similar to the World Tourism Day, to be organized periodically in an African country each year.
- Encouraging joint tourism programs between Egypt and the African countries for foreign tourists and African tourists, so that the tourism program includes more than a tourism destination including Egypt and African countries.

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الملخص العربي

رؤية مستقبلية لتنشيط السياحة البيئية بين مصر وأفريقيا محمود رمضان العزب

مدرس بقسم الدراسات السياحية – كلية السياحة والفنادق – جامعة مدينة السادات

الملخص

تحاول الدراسة الحالية التأكيد على أهمية السوق الأفريقية لصناعة السياحة المصرية إلى جانب الأسواق السياحية الأخرى ، وتحقيق التكامل الإفريقي من خلال السياحة البيئية. الهدف الرئيسي من هذه الدراسة هو تقديم الرؤى والاستراتيجيات المستقبلية لتعزيز السياحة البيئية بين مصر وأفريقيا، حيث توفر السياحة البيئية الاهتمام الاجتماعي وفرص الترفيه، ودعم البنية التحتية المجتمعية والصناعة، وتساهم في تحقيق التماسك الاجتماعي والاعتزاز الوطني. تم جمع البيانات من خلال قائمة الاستبيانات والمقابلات مع الخبراء في وزارة السياحة، وبعض الباحثين المصريين والأفارقة بمعهد الدراسات الأفريقية بجامعة القاهرة. كشفت النتائج أن السياحة البيئية تلعب دوراً مهماً في التعامل مع العديد من المشكلات السياسية والاقتصادية والاجتماعية والثقافية والبيئية بين مصر والدول الإفريقية. وأشارت إلى أن أهم العقبات التي تواجه تعزيز السياحة البيئية هي الافتقار إلى الحملات التسويقية، غياب السياسات والخطط المتعلقة بوضع السياحة الأفريقية على خريطة السياحة المصرية، والإجراءات المعقدة للحصول على تأشيرة دخول لمصر. كما أشارت النتائج إلى بعض الرؤى المستقبلية لتعزيز السياحة داخل المنطقة، وأبرزها إجراء الكثير من دراسات السوق حول المجتمعات الأفريقية، تنفيذ حملة تسويقية منظمة للسوق الأفريقية، حل المشكلات والتوترات السياسية بين مصر و الدول الإفريقية، تنظيم رحلات منتظمة بأسعار تنافسية، وتشجيع برامج السياحة المشتركة بين مصر والدول الأفريقية للسياح الأجانب. أخيراً، تختتم الدراسة بمقترحات لصناع القرار في مصر لإيلاء الاهتمام لتشجيع السياحة البيئية بين مصر والدول الإفريقية.

الكلمات الدالة: السياحة، السياحة البيئية، مصر، أفريقيا، حركة السياحة الأفريقية